

IMPLEMENTATION OF VOIP SERVICE IN MOBILE AD-HOC NETWORK

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Abstract:

Over Internet (VOIP) is an emerging popular Internet application that provides good services through Mobile Adhoc Network(MANET).MANET provides a suitable platform for the deployment of voice and multimedia session over IP network in many application scenarios that range from safety to comfort related services. But this network also faces many challenges on QoS issues due to packet loss because of transmission errors, short battery life and dynamic changing topologies. WiMAX is a wireless 4G technology, currently using by various industries & institutions which provides many advantages due to its high speed and large coverage area. Combining these technology together, in this paper we estimated the performance of various VOIP codecs with WiMAX in different scenarios (sparse and dense) over MANET. Mobile ad-hoc networks one can extend the reach of existing fixed telephony. This whole mechanism of extending the reach of fixed telephony is also termed as Fixed to Mobile Convergence FMC)

Key words: IP address allocation; MANET, VoIP, QoS, Codecs, WiMAX

1 . INTRODUCTION

Wireless communication enables a user to access the communication services at anytime from anywhere around the world. Now a day's user can move around all over the world while maintaining the connectivity with the rest of the world. This type of communication is categorized as Mobile Computing Network. Existing mobile computing network can be classified into –

- a) Infrastructure based network.
- b) Mobile Adhoc network(MANETs).

Mobile Ad hoc networks are a special category of networks exclusively classified on the basis of attributes like infrastructure-less-ness and Dynamic topology. A MANET may be suitable for networks within airports, meeting rooms, and open spaces due to both economical and technological feasibilities. Because the MANET is based upon IP protocol suites, a node in the MANET cannot take part in unicast communications until it is configured with a free IP address. MANETs are decentralized network consisting of mobile nodes equipped with wireless communication without any access point or any existing infrastructure. This self organizing capability of MANET makes it suitable for various circumstances like to set up a network on emergency basis, for military environment, for civilian environment such as taxi cab network, meeting rooms and for personal area networking like cell phone, laptop, earphone, wrist watch etc.

A problem associated with IP address assignment of a mobile node is that the IP address may change during its session in the MANET. IP address change is not a serious problem in hardwired networks because the IP address of a host is either statically configured or dynamically allocated by a DHCP server. It usually does not change its IP address during a session unless it reboots. However, because the nodes in the MANET are free to move arbitrarily, IP address change happens more frequently when applied with auto configuration, global connectivity, and hierarchical addressing schemes

There are several scenarios in which a mobile node will change its IP address:

(1) Merger of two partitions of a network If some mobile nodes in the MANET move out of the transmission range of the other nodes, the network becomes partitioned as illustrated in Fig. 1(a). Because these nodes may not be aware of the partition, they may still use the previous allocated addresses. If the IP address of a node (say node A) in one partition is allocated to the new node (say node B) in the other partition, address conflict occurs when these two partitions become connected, as illustrated in Fig.1 (b). One example is when some attendants leave a meeting room for a short period and then return during a presentation session. The prophet address allocation is insensitive to this scenario, while the nodes in one partition may need to change their addresses with DDHCP.

Figure 1. A network is partitioned and then merged

(2) Merger of two independent MANETs

The second scenario is that two independently configured MANETs merge. Because these two networks are auto-configured separately, there may be some duplicate addresses in both networks, such as node A in MANET 1 and node B in MANET 2 in Fig. 2. Thus, one needs to change its address due to the merger.

Figure 2. Merger of two independent MANET

2. Related Work

- 1.
- 2.

2.1 Voice over IP over MANET

Manet provides a suitable platform for the deployment of VOIP applications in many scenarios as the quality of service requirements is a major challenge for real time applications. This section provides a brief overview of VOIP implementation, voice codecs, H.323 signaling protocol.

VOIP-Now a day's subscriber wants to communicate via e-mail, instant messaging, video etc. in addition to the voice traffic. For this type of multimedia communication VOIP technology is most appropriate that allows communication over packet switched network between two parties. It is a methodology that allows the transmission of voice and multimedia sessions over Internet that reduces the cost of long distance voice calls or sometimes offers free of cost service irrespective of the distance.

Voice communication in a VOIP system can be illustrated by a block diagram fig 1. Initially human voice remains in the analog form so before transmitting this voice over packet switched analog signal has to be digitized at the sender side and the reverse process (depacketized and decoded) is performed at the receiver side. Digitization process is composed of sampling, quantization and encoding. The quality of voice communication over IP is mainly influenced by the choice of voice codec.

CODECS- The application of voice codec process is the initial step for voice communication. It's primary function is convert the incoming analog voice pattern into digital stream and vice versa .International Telecommunication Unions (ITU-T) has developed various encoding techniques which are classified into waveform coders (eg-G.726,G.711), Vocoders and Hybrid Coders(eg-G.723,G.728,G.729).As the number of mobile nodes varies quality of the voice also gets affected. So the choice of codec is the significant factor whose main objective is to perform voice digitization and compression ensuring the lowest bit rate possible without degrading the signal quality.

Signaling protocol- The encoded speech in the form of packets is when transmitted over IP network requires appropriate signaling protocol like H.323 or SIP(J. Rosenberg *et al*,2002).In this paper we had used H.323 multimedia signaling protocol and WiMAX network.H.323 is a ITU-T's recommended standard protocol for set up and tear down calls of IP telephony. It is responsible for encoding, decoding, packetizing, signaling & control as well as capabilities exchange of audio and video signals (Davidson Jonathan *et al*; ITU-T Recommendation, 1998).

3. Simulation Methodology

For the evaluation of VOIP applications performance over MANET Qualnet simulation tool 6.1 is used which determines the behavior of system in virtual computational world.

Qualnet is a network simulator which provides a comprehensive environment for developing protocols and analyzing the performance of network scenario

In order to analyze the performance of VOIP application over MANET we proposed framework approach.

Step1- First step involves the scenario creation which encapsulates the following stages-

a. Node configuration and general parameters- This includes configuration of parameters like simulation time, area, terrain as well as placement of nodes and connecting them to the wireless network through links.

b. VOIP Application- In the next stage VOIP applications are placed from node to node according to the requirement for transferring the multimedia

data.

c. Configuration of subnet and network protocol- In this stage properties of wireless subnet are configured which encapsulates the configuration of each layer like PHY, MAC, NETWORK, and Routing protocol. Phy and Mac layer are set to 802.16(WIMAX), Network layer is set to IPV4 protocol and Bellman-ford(Raghavendra Ganiga *et al*,2012) as routing protocol.H.323 is set as multimedia signaling protocol in Application layer.

d. Channel Configuration- Channel configuration depends upon the no of base stations used connected through wired links. Then configuration will be changed through scenario properties. No of channel will be set via array editor and channel frequency (1.95-2.5) will be assigned to each channel individually.

Step2- Second step involves the creation of station in which particular nodes will be selected and their property will be changed to „set as base station“ in MAC layer. Then remaining nodes will be selected and their Mobility and Placement property will be set to Random way point.

Step3- This step includes the setting of scenario properties in which Battery model is enabled via statistics and tracking property. Then scenario is compiled and executed which encapsulates real time and execution time. This turns the simulator from design mode to visualization mode.

Step4- After the execution of scenario statistics of various metrics are collected from Analyzer. Statistics are the simulation result according to the layer properties.

Step5- This step specifies the result of different statistics of various scenarios with varying voice codec. Results with varying metrics values are compared that helps in concluding the best voice codec.

4. Auto-configuration Protocols & Architectures

There are numerous Auto-configuration protocols for MANET IP address configuration. Cano Reyes et proposed a blue tooth based Auto-configuration architecture for MANETs known as Easy MANET. For configuration of unique IP address the architecture relies on the use of a blue tooth server. The architecture also binds IP address with a user photo and it is referred as Visual DNS system. The discovery mechanism works by exchanging UDP messages. The content of the message contains list of available MANET members. In case a node finds a new member the details are downloaded using TCP connection. The dependency of the Bluetooth server for configuration tasks means if there is non-availability of Bluetooth server then node configuration is not possible.

L. Villalba et al. proposed Distributed dynamic host configuration protocol (D2HCP). Each node possesses disjoint set of IP addresses. In case a new node wants to join the MANET then it initiates MAC based communication with the nodes available in its radio range. In case the neighbour node has free available addresses it assigns it to the new node. In case of non availability of addresses a network wide broadcast for IP address is conducted. Upon reception of available IP addresses the new node is assigned an IP address. The

protocol uses OLSR for node synchronization and duplicate address detection. Same author has proposed an extension to D2HCP with network merging support.

M. Al-Mistarihi et al. proposed a tree based topology oriented auto-configuration mechanism. Each node can have any of three roles which are root node, leader node or normal node. Root node is the main node in the protocol which maintains the records of the leader nodes and their address information in its database and performs tasks of network partitioning and merging. Leader nodes possess disjoint set of IP addresses for assignment of IP addresses to incoming nodes. Normal nodes do not have any special function except used for routing in case of non-availability of leader in a particular area. U. Ghosh et.al proposed scheme named as ID based IP configuration scheme (IDDIP). The scheme is based on a one way hash function installed at each node prior deployment of MANET. Each node is capable of assigning IP address to the incoming node and act as a proxy node. Proxy node authenticates the incoming node using public key cryptography; similarly the incoming node also authenticates the sanctity of the proxy node in the same manner. Along with a unique IP address, each node is identified by a unique ID tuple i.e. $\langle \text{node ID}, \text{IP address} \rangle$.

4.1 ID/Locator Based Protocols & Architectures

The overriding role of IP address as an ID as well as identifier is not only the problem of MANET but the infrastructure based networks are also facing problem due to this peculiar attribute and it is a bottleneck in the design of Future Wireless Networks (FWN). Leading network researchers have provided critique on the overriding role of IP address . A number of architectures based on the separation or disassociation of the Identifier and Locator of IP address have been proposed and a new field of ID/Locator Split Concept has emerged. The basis of such architectures is the seminal paper of I. Stoica et.al in which internet Indirection Infrastructure (I3) was presented.

The basic architecture of I3 is based on rendezvous based communication. Merriam Webster [21] defines rendezvous as:

“A place appointed for assembling or meeting” This model and the recent models which follow I3 architecture are based on the introduction of an infrastructure which performs the role of indirection. A receiver can place a trigger, which is a pair of its address and its identifier (id,R) into I3 infrastructure. The sender can send the data to the receiver based upon pair of (id,data). When the data is received by the I3 it provides an indirection and sends the data to the receiver. Below figure illustrate the indirection and I3 model respectively.

Important Design Considerations and

Challenges

In order to design an auto-configurable architecture for Mobile ad hoc networks based on ID/Locator split concept various adaptations and modifications are necessary. ID/Locator split concept is based on the usage of indirection infrastructure in the form of servers, where as in case of Mobile ad hoc networks infrastructure is not available, therefore current ID/Locators architecture cannot be directly-applied in MANET context.

Another aspect which is necessary in MANET environment is to provide efficient services. As MANETs are ad hoc networks where there are sparse power resources. If uncompressed data is sent through the nodes then batteries of nodes will drain in a drastic manner. To ensure efficiency, compression schemes for header compressions are required.

There are various problems of adopting header compression schemes in MANET which mainly are dynamic topology, node failure and loss of packet and control information. Moreover, these schemes are IP oriented thus in order to make their usage possible nodes should have unique addresses configured in their interfaces for proper routing of data packets upon change of IP addresses as continuity of compression/decompression cannot be guaranteed. Moreover, if such a compression scheme is adopted then it will become necessary to compress and decompress the IP Packets at every hop which is an unnecessary processing overhead.

4.2 Sub Systems of ID Based Protocol

Architecture

4.2.1 Private Address Map

Linux system gives provision such that a node can configure virtual Ethernet locally and can privately assign IP Addresses to the virtual interfaces. The same provision is used in our design and a single node can configure a number of private IP addresses for other nodes in MANET. A node will instantiate a virtual interface and can assign a unique private address for the node for which it requires communication. As the unique assignment is done privately at the node level therefore no further address detection is required in the whole MANET. Private address MAP also gives provision of running IP oriented applications

4.2.2 Network Address & ID Translation (NAIDT)

Each end host communicates using identifiers. At the start of communication each host configure into the other hosts NAIDT module its Private IP address. A NAIDT system keeps mapping between the Identifier and Private IP addresses at each node using a NAIDT table. This table is a Map type data structure for fast retrieval and insertion. Another function of NAIDT system is to insert the particular Identifiers to the packet being processed.

5. MANET Routing Protocols

Routing in MANET

One of the significant challenges in MANET is developing support for routing because of the combination of different characteristics in the network such as frequent change of topology, lack of infrastructure in place to aid the communication and the movement of the nodes in the network. The biggest challenge that causes high frequent route failure in a dynamic network with rapid topological changes is mobility. Any routing protocol developed to support this type of communication should be bandwidth-efficient and must produce low overhead to deliver good overall performance. The routing protocols designed for wired networks are not capable to perform in MANET due to their incapacity of producing low overhead to speed up the communication which leads to different proposals for optimizing different protocol to suit MANET

Routing in MANET can be classified into two different categories, which are; Unicast and Multicast routing. Both embrace some form of flooding techniques to deliver a packet from source to destination. Flooding which is referred to as network-wide broadcasting is a process or method of delivery data from one node to another in a communication environment. It uses MAC protocol layer as a broadcast mechanism to transfer packet from a

source node to the neighbouring nodes. Broadcasting information has to be once then it will re-broadcast through another node and terminate when every node has heard the packet in order to overcome looping problem. The purpose of using flooding techniques is to eliminate the redundant broadcast and to ensure that all the nodes in the network participate actively.

While Unicast routing is the process of maintaining a single route in a network between all pairs of nodes regardless of whether all routes are actually used; Multicast routing referred to single source with multiple destinations to deliver a packet in a network environment. Unicast routing technique is highly significant because it maintain a shortest path to destination. All proactive routing protocols are unicast routing in nature and are classified into distance vector and link state protocols. Examples of unicast routing protocols are Destination-Sequence Distance-Vector (DSDV), Wireless Routing Protocol (WRP), Optimized Link State Routing (OLSR), and Topology Broadcast based on Routing-Path Forwarding (TBRPF).

5.1 The Proactive Routing Protocols:

The Proactive routing protocols keep visiting each and every node in the Network by sending Hello Messages to the nodes. The frequent change in topology would usually amount to a high cost of network maintenance. Therefore when there is a need for a route to a destination; such route information will immediately learn and adapt the changes without affecting the transmission process. The following are proactive routing protocols: *Wireless Routing Protocol (WRP)*, *Destination-Sequenced Distance-Vector Routing (DSDV)*, *Optimized Link State Routing Protocol (OLSR)*, *Fisheye State Routing (FSR)*, *Global State Routing (GSR)*, *Hierarchical State Routing (HSR)* and *Topology Broadcast Reverse Forwarding (TBRF)*.

5.2 The Reactive Routing Protocols:

The reactive routing protocols are centred on request transmission processes also referred to as Query-reply dialog protocols. Protocol reaction emerges only when there is a request or demand by a node in the network, and it does not require any periodic transmission of topological information through the network. These protocols are sometime referred to as on-demand routing protocols. The following are reactive protocols: Ad-Hoc On-Demand Distance Vector Routing (AODV), Dynamic Source Routing (DSR), Admission Control enabled On-demand Routing (ACOR), *Associativity-Based Routing (ABR)*, *Location-Aided Routing (LAR)*, and Temporally-Ordered Routing Algorithm (TORA).

5.3 Hybrid routing Protocol:

Hybrid routing protocols are protocols that are both reactive and proactive in nature. Schematic nature of protocols was aimed at increasing scalability of MANET routing protocols in order to allow neighboring nodes of the same quality to form a backbone capable of reducing route discovery overhead. Reactive protocols are more scalable than proactive protocols because of their architecture.

CONCLUSION:

In this paper we have demonstrated the design and implementation of an ID based MANET auto-configuration protocol for solving the IP based auto-configuration issues in MANET context. The implemented design uses identifiers like national identity card number, vehicle number, student ID card number for establishing communication between end points. An ID based routing and packet forwarding mechanism is also designed and implemented. The implemented architecture supports conventional IP based applications and users can run these applications in MANET scenario as if the MANET nodes are present in a LAN based environment. mobile nodes in MANETs may change their IP addresses more frequently than fixed hosts in hardwired networks. However, the issue of address change has not been carefully studied. Based upon the analysis of the overhead caused by address change, we introduced the Route Shift packet, Address Change Message, and NAT scheme to solve the problem.

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